

OPPORTUNITIES AND DIRECTIONS FOR USING MARKETING STRATEGIES TO INCREASE REGIONAL EXPORT POTENTIAL

Jiyamuratov R.N.

Doctoral student of SamIES

rustamnuridinovich9@gmail.com

Abstract: This article discusses the specific features of developing marketing strategies to increase regional export potential, ways to use the matrix "level of demand - level of demand dynamics" in developing marketing strategies for regional export potential.

Keywords: regional export potential, defining strategic directions, marketing strategy, expanding exports, optimizing the supply of goods, differentiation and diversification strategies in expanding the geography of exports.

A number of scientific studies are being conducted in the world to develop specific marketing strategies to increase regional export potential, to establish free economic zones in the regions, to organize the production of intellectual resources, innovations, high-value-added goods in the regions and their sales in foreign markets.

Literature analysis. A number of scientific studies are being carried out on marketing strategies aimed at the socio-economic development of the region.

According to the leading marketing expert F. Kotler, the general marketing strategies for regional development are as follows [5]:

- attracting tourists and business visitors;
- attracting business from other places;
- maintaining and expanding existing businesses;

- encouraging the development of small businesses and facilitating new enterprises;
- increasing exports and the flow of third-party investments;
- increasing the population or changing the composition of the population.

For each of these strategies, it is possible to formulate a marketing strategy that provides an appropriate direction and the introduction of its representatives into foreign markets.

F. Kotler, in his research on marketing strategies used to increase the export potential of the region, draws attention to the need to identify current and potential exporters [5]. He emphasizes the importance of co-branding in exporting products and identifies ten functions that regional authorities can perform to help companies develop exports:

1. Information provider - providing companies with information about export markets;
2. Broker - searching for counterparties and distributors for small businesses;
3. Promotion - integration of local manufacturers with foreign representative offices and trade fairs;
4. Instructor and consultant - conducting seminars and conferences, training;
5. Financier - lending, incentives, guarantees;
6. Host - organizing exhibitions and fairs, receiving foreign entrepreneurs;
7. Goal setting - goal orientation for promoting the leading clusters of the region;
8. Promoter - trade marketing;
9. Developer - development of a place as a transport hub in trade relations between other regions;
10. Developer of new technologies - testing new technologies in the region.

Analysis and conclusion. One of the important conditions for ensuring sustainable economic growth in the economy of Uzbekistan is the development of

regional exports. Currently, the growth of the economy of Uzbekistan is mainly associated with the export of resources with low added value. It is objectively necessary to change the composition of exports due to an increase in the share of goods with high added value. Because structural changes in global production and technological chains are not only a source of resources for the regions, but also a leader in developing new markets for high-tech goods with high consumption potential, which ensures long-term economic growth. Consequently, increasing regional export potential is achieved not only through the export of resources, but also through the production of competitive high-tech products and their introduction to the world market.

According to the results of the research conducted in the previous chapters and sections, the following theoretical and methodological problems were identified regarding the formation and development of regional export potential:

1) Existing methodological approaches to the formation of regional export potential mainly study the composition of exports and their impact on export indicators (volume, sales price, profitability of supply of export goods, etc.) without assessing the impact on the structural structure. ;

2) The lack of a scientifically based selection of high-tech products for the development of export potential creates uncertainty in determining strategic directions for state support of regional exporters.

3) Failure to develop marketing strategies related to the production of products and their sale in foreign markets to increase regional export potential.

Among them, the development of marketing strategies related to the use of export potential to ensure the economic growth of the region is of great importance. In this regard, one of the important tasks of scientific research is to develop the region's export potential and expand the production of value-added products that are in high demand in foreign markets, to introduce products to the world market and increase production volumes. development of global markets.

In the "Effective demand dynamics - effective demand level" matrix, the priority of the types of goods for the expansion of regional exports is evaluated based on the location of export goods. Based on the cross-classification of the volume and dynamics of demand for the types and assortment of export goods, it becomes possible to determine the priority goods.

The matrix for placing export products in the levels of the effective demand level coordinates of the effective demand dynamics includes 4 standard positions. In addition, the placement of export goods in the quadrants of the matrix makes it possible to justify various forms of export expansion and the choice of the direction of industrial cooperation.

At the fourth stage of development of marketing strategies to increase the regional export potential, the risks of regional export goods producers in the markets of importing countries are assessed.

Thus, the methodology for developing a marketing strategy for increasing regional export potential is based on two directions:

the first direction - the use of priority assortments of existing export goods, characterized by a significant specific share in the volume of regional exports, stable effective demand corresponding to the stages of growth or maturity in world markets, as the basis of export potential;

the second direction is to include in the region's export portfolio new promising high-value-added goods that are competitive in the world goods and services markets and are at the top of world exports.

List of used literature.

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 11, 2023 No. PF-158 "On the strategy of Uzbekistan-2030"// www.lex.uz
2. Bianchi, Constanza and Garcia, Rodrigo (2007) Export Marketing Strategies of an Emerging Country: An Exploratory Study of the Main Challenges

and Factors Leading to Success for Chilean Food Exporters. *Journal of Food Products Marketing* 13(3): pp. 1-19.

3. Bibek Ray Chaudhuri, Debottam Chakraborty. *Export Potential at the State-Level: A Case Study of Karnataka*. Indian Institute of Foreign Trade. 2010, 1-26 pp.

4. Gouvea R. Reassessing export diversification strategies: a cross-country comparison / R. Gouvea, G. Vora // *Modern Economy*. 2015. Vol. 6. P. 96-118.

5. Kotler F., Asplund K., Rein I. i dr. *Marketing site: private investment, business, hotel and tourism in the city, municipality, regional and European countries*. - SPb.: Izd. "Economics of the Stockholm School", 2005. - 376 p

